

TANICENGKEH.COM: MARKETING INNOVATION USING TECHNOLOGY TO EMPOWER INDONESIAN CLOVE FARMERS (STUDY CASE : BULELENG DISTRICT, BALI)

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Abstract

As an agricultural country, Indonesia has great opportunities in developing the export of agricultural products, particularly from the plantation subsector. One of the export commodities estate subsectors is clove. The contribution of cloves in Indonesia in the year 2016 contributed export value with volume amounting 8,477 tons with a value of US \$24,060. Buleleng Regency is one of the regencies in Indonesia produce clove production of 4,907 tons in 2015. However, clove farmers in the Buleleng Regency are still experiencing problems on the distribution of marketing who farmers still sell cloves to the middleman. The purpose of this paper is to optimize the potential sale of clove technology-based platform that helps farmers to sell the clove through the website tanicengkeh.com. Tanicengkeh.com also has a function to provide technical-related information about planting, processing, to marketing which is good. This paper is a library research presented descriptively and supported by some literature relevant to the study of the problem. Data processing technique is conduct by descriptive analysis. Implementation of tanicengkeh.com in Buleleng Regency can be more optimal in managing the production and marketing of cloves, so it will increase income and reach better welfare to the clove farmers in Buleleng, Bali.

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.2541300

1. Introduction

Indonesia is developing an agricultural country where agriculture as the object source of livelihood of the majority of the population. The role of the agricultural sector towards the national development can be seen from his contributions to the amount of absorption of labor. There is five categories business field where is agriculture sector ranks first in building a nationwide through its contribution to the amount of absorption of labor in Indonesia. Its contributions are as follows:

Figure 1. The amount of labor absorption the year 2017

Based on the figure 1 shows the role of agriculture, plantations, forestry, hunting, and fishing contribute toward the labors, from totally 121,022,423 labors, the agricultural sector absorb 35,923,886 labor or 35% of the total labor that exists in Indonesia and then on third rank trade, restaurants, accommodation services are 28,173,571 or 28% of the total labor that exists in Indonesia while the industrial sector was only able to absorb as much as 17% of the total number of labor while 20% or 19,434,145 is filled by various sectors of the field of business in Indonesia. [1] This absorption proves that the agricultural sector give important contribution for Indonesia, so the Government needs to pay the maximum attention for this sector with policies do not burden the subject in this sector. [2]

One of regency in Bali Province that has the potential agricultural producers is Buleleng regency. Buleleng is very potential for developing cloves commodity, it can be seen from the clove plantation's vast Bali has 15,668 ha, and about 49.48 percent or 7,754.82 were in Buleleng Regency. Buleleng Regency's clove production contributes amount 4,907 tons or about 80.35 percent of the total production on Bali amount of 5,871.30 tons. [3]

Beside from the number of potential are still found some problems faced by farmers in Buleleng Regency which is the bargaining power of producers very low and on the process of price determining form farmers controlled by intermediary merchants (the middleman) and bargaining power between producers and consumers almost vanish. These problems become clove farmers in Buleleng Regency indirectly suffered loss because of the differences in price from the middleman cheaper than the market price.

As a step to increase income and welfare of farmers living in Buleleng Regency can be done through technological innovation to give pieces of information such as planning, processing up to integrated marketing using the role of *tanicengkeh.com*. *Tanicengkeh.com* is a platform that has a purpose to sell farmer's clove to consumers with the best price and does not damage the farmers, on the other hand, *tanicengkeh.com* also provides experience and knowledge for clove farmers.

1.1 Problem Identification

Based on the background above, the problems of this research are as follows :

1. What are the problems faced by clove farmers in Buleleng Regency?
2. How the implementation of *tanicengkeh.com* website as a strategy to increase clove farmer's income in Buleleng Regency?

2. Theoretical Review

2.1 Marketing

The process by which companies create value for customers and build strong customer relationships in order to capture value from customers in return. [4] "Marketing is the process of identifying, creating and communicating the values, as well as maintaining relationships that satisfy the customer to maximize corporate profits". [5] Some definitions of marketing are expressed by some experts, it can be concluded that the marketing is a processor function of the social organization in the activities of the business which aims to distribute goods to satisfy consumer needs. They are two kinds of marketing, as follows :

1. Online Marketing

Online marketing is a part of the e-commerce company, namely for communication, promotion, and selling goods and services over the internet. Online marketing is the application that runs the online booking process to help the companies. [6]

2. Direct marketing

"Direct relationship with consumers individually is targeted carefully to grab the immediate response and achieve a lasting customer relationship". [7] In other words, direct selling is a direct communication with the individual customer who shot carefully both to obtain an immediate response or build a long customer relationship. In the direct marketing channels typically use channels directly to reach out and hand over the goods and services to customers without

intermediary marketing. That channel includes direct mail, catalogs, telemarketing, interactive tv, internet sites, and others.

3. Research Method

Data Collection techniques using qualitative methods in the form of in-depth interviews, where the data comes from one of the farmers in Buleleng. Data processing was carried out by descriptive analysis and analysis of fishbone diagrams. Fishbone analysis diagrams are used at the problem identification stage to determine the cause of the emergence of the problem. The type of data used includes primary and secondary data. Primary data is obtained through observation and interview with the object of study. Secondary data obtained from various credible sources include printed books, journals, and articles, official local and international websites.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1 Problem of Clove Farmers Development in Buleleng Regency Use Fishbone Diagram

Preventing factors to develop the clove farmers in Buleleng Regency can be outlined as follows: 1) Product, still the difference quality clove which causes problems are complained by clove farmers. 2) Price, the price is set by the middleman for farmers have difference high quite against the selling price of the middleman to large merchants. 3) Place, clove farmers do not have a place to sell the results of cloves except in middleman, so the middleman has authority to determine the price of cloves. 4) Promotion, the absence of information is regarding the sale of clove in Buleleng Regency, so after the middleman buys cloves from farmers next middleman sell the cloves to the cigarettes factories and it happens monopoly price. 5) People, the farmers is lack of knowledge, so there are still many cases of a failed harvest. 6) Physical Evidence, the quality, and marketing of clove are still needed improvement in order to increase farmers income.

Source: Author's Analysis

Having outlined the various factors cause-related marketing barriers Buleleng Regency, the next step is to know the main factors (potentially) the most dominant of the various problems have been described. Focus group discussion be steps to knowing it. The results form the conclusion that the most dominant factor namely the promotion is still low, the lack of publication, and use of technology.

4.2 Implementation of Tanicengkeh.com as a means of Clove Farmers Marketing in Buleleng Regency

Figure 2. The Clove Marketing Schemes Through The Website Tanicengkeh.com Source: Author's Analysis

Based on figure 2 above, can be explained as follows: 1) farmers who have joined Tanicengkeh.com reported sales of cloves to the website Tanicengkeh.com and then managed by the community. 2) Consumers buy cloves belong to farmers who have been managed by the community through the website Tanicengkeh.com.

4.3 Implementation of the Tanicengkeh.com as a Means of Learning the Clove Farmers in Buleleng Regency in Using Synergy Pentahelix

Figure 3 Learning Scheme for cloves farmers through the Website Tanicengkeh.com Source: Author's Analysis

Based on Figure 3 above, can be described as follows; 1) farmers who have joined the Tanicengkeh.com can access the material which is according to the problems being experienced through the website Tanicengkeh.com. In addition, there are spaces consulting for farmers who are still having problems from planting to the marketing process. In order to make the process run smoothly then needed synergy between stakeholders namely of Academician, Business, Government, Community, and Media or referred to as synergy pentahelix:

1. Academician, through the experience and the capacity of the scientific societies, is expected to collaborate in undertaking Research and Development of technology and marketing.
2. Business, partnering with clove farmers from other regions.
3. Government, include local governments and ministry-related acts; 1) Regulation Role, the form of marketing policy oversight, 2) Allocation Role, related distribution experts, technology, and infrastructure.
4. Community, act as a catalyst through the event organizers as well as the manager of the website Tanicengkeh.com
5. Media, serve as middlemen to communicate towards the community about the existence of Tanicengkeh.com as a platform to market their produce.

4.4 Tanicengkeh.com: Clove Farmers Welfare Development Platform in Buleleng Regency

Tanicengkeh.com is a clove farmer welfare development platform in Buleleng Regency online. Creating and maintaining websites at once are carried out by the Community. Clove farmers can do marketing and get learning after fulfilling the requirements as follows; 1) Register by filling the form has been provided online on the website *tanicengkeh.com*. 2) Verify the data by uploading a photo and identification card

5. Conclusion

The concept of farmer development in the area of Buleleng Regency is built on the basis of potential local resources that have not been utilized to its full potential especially in the process of distribution of products and the quality of human resources is still low. The use of E-commerce in the form of tanicengkeh.com be important applied using empowerment technology. The first step is done by identifying the factors that impede the development farmers in the area of Buleleng Regency, so its measures can be determined. Next steps the stakeholder synergy (Academician, Business, Government, Community, and the Media) to optimize the various potential especially in improving the quality of human resources who will then produce a strategy. More than that, it can be used as a reference for the development of the region with the concept of empowerment technology in other Indonesia territory.

6. Recommendation

The advice in the writing of this website is the application of *tanicengkeh.com* in helping to market the clove and learning to give farmers necessary synergy between stakeholders. The Government need to endorse and help promote the website *tanicengkeh.com* in order to replace the middleman position in society. Community and the media need to do such an approach that the middleman does to communities faster get to know website *tanicengkeh.com*. Academician and business are required to provide learning to the clove farmers. With the synergy of the stakeholders then the website *tanicengkeh.com* can help increase the income of clove farmers and welfare increases.

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